

The Effect of Counseling Using Video Health Promotion Media on Increasing Knowledge and Attitudes of Pregnant Women about The First 1000 Days of Life in Meukek District

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ABSTRACT

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The first 1000 days of life is a sensitive period that determines the child's future life, where the impact of this period on the baby will last a long time and cannot be overcome. Improved nutrition is implemented through a holistic care strategy that focuses on the first 1000 days of life starting from the pregnancy period until the child is 2 years old. This research aims to determine the impact of increasing the knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women through the use of video health promotion media. This research uses a quasi-experimental design with a two-group pre-test and post-test. The sample was allocated into two intervention groups: the first group received an education intervention with video health promotion media, and the other group received an education intervention without video media. The research sample consisted of 126 pregnant women who received antenatal care at Posyandu. Statistical analysis of the data was carried out using Mann Whitney and Wilcoxon analysis. The results showed that the level of knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women regarding the first 1000 days of life had a significant effect after receiving counseling intervention using video health promotion media ($P < 0.001$). In conclusion, counseling using video health promotion media and counseling without video media about the first 1000 days of life can increase the knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women in Meukek District.

KEYWORDS:

First 1000 Days of Life, Counseling, Knowledge, Attitude

INTRODUCTION

The National Food and Nutrition Action Plan plays an important role in aligning food and nutrition development initiatives at the central and regional levels, covering various stages such as planning, implementation, monitoring and assessment. This effort aims to address the reduction in stunting rates, which is being actively pursued to achieve the national targets outlined in the National Medium Term Development Plan, which aims to reduce the prevalence of stunting under five to 14.0% by 2024. In addition, local governments will utilize

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the Plan National Action for Food and Nutrition in formulating Regional Action Plans for Food and Nutrition (Bappenas, 2021).

Assessment of future human health status relies heavily on nutritional consumption during the first 1000 days of life. As outlined by the Directorate of Nutrition and Public Health, the First Thousand Days of Life covers a period of 1000 days from conception in the womb until the child reaches the age of 2 years. This period consists of 270 days (9 months) of pregnancy and 730 days (2 years) of postnatal life from birth. Referred to as the Golden Period or critical phase, failure to properly utilize this period can cause irreversible damage. An individual's nutritional status can be an indication of their potential as human resources. As a result, appropriate intervention during early childhood can significantly impact their future quality of life. The early years of life pose a high risk for a variety of nutritional challenges (Bappenas, 2021).

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Good nutrition serves as the foundation for each person to realize his or her maximum potential. The first 1000 days of life represent a critical period that shapes a child's future quality of life, with permanent and irreversible effects. Improved nutrition is achieved through a sustainable care system that focuses on the first 1,000 days of life, from conception until the child is 2 years old (Kemenkes RI, 2019).

Presidential Regulation no. 42 of 2013 issued by the Indonesian Government, relating to the National Movement to accelerate improved nutrition, with special emphasis on the first 1000 days of a person's life. This initiative facilitates collaborative efforts between the government and the general public by encouraging active participation and systematically addressing stakeholder interests, all aimed at improving the nutritional status of the population, with a special focus on the first 1000 days of life (Kemenkes RI, 2020).

The implementation of this movement consists of specific nutrition interventions and sensitive nutrition interventions. Specific nutrition interventions are specific measures aimed at direct prevention and reduction of nutritional problems. Typically, these initiatives are implemented by health departments. Examples of these actions include vaccinations, providing additional food to pregnant women and toddlers at posyandu. The main focus lies in achieving the target group in the first 1000 days of life (pregnant women, breastfeeding mothers, and children aged 0-23 months). A good nutrition program is an activity carried out outside the health sector but which directly and collectively provides a significant impact on the first 1,000 days of life, such as nutrition and health education, food safety, and so on (Rossha et al., 2016).

To reduce and address nutritional problems in the first 1000 days of life, potential strategies involve providing health education focused on promoting balanced nutrition in the first 1000 days of life. According to Notoatmodjo (2012), health education functions as an important information instrument that has proven effective in improving certain dimensions of health that require further attention.

In 2022 in Meukek District there will be 6 cases of infant deaths and 16 cases of babies with low birth weight. This proves that

the knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women still have limitations regarding the first 1000 days of life. Insufficient knowledge and attitudes can affect the quality of care for pregnant women during pregnancy and childbirth early in life. It is hoped that providing education can increase knowledge and it is hoped that attitudes will change for the better (Dinkes Aceh Selatan, 2023).

Based on the background above, the author conducted research with the title "The Effect of Counseling Using Video Health Promotion Media on Increasing Knowledge and Attitudes of Pregnant Women About the First 1000 Days of Life in Meukek District."

METHOD

This research used a quasi-experimental design with a Two-Group Pre-test and Post-test by providing interventions using video health promotion media and without video media regarding 1000 HPK on the knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women. The research sample consisted of 126 pregnant women who received antenatal care at Posyandu in the working area of Meukek Community Health Center and Drien Jalo Community Health Center in 2024 and met the established criteria. The sampling method used is non-probability sampling with an accidental sampling method.

Providing counseling interventions to respondents about the first 1000 days of life in group A with 5 (five) minute video media via laptop/cellphone and in group B counseling without video media. Researchers carried out a final evaluation with the same questionnaire as during the pretest.

The processed data was then tested univariately and bivariately by carrying out Mann Whitney and Wilcoxon statistical tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

The characteristics of respondents in this study were measured based on age, education, employment and income. Data regarding the characteristics of respondents can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1. Distribution Based on Characteristics or Confounding Variables

Demographics/ Confounding Variable	Research Group					
	Extension Intervention with Video		Extension Intervention Without Video Media		Total	
	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)
Education						
Junior High School	8	12,7	8	12,7	16	12,7
Senior High School	53	84,1	53	84,1	106	84,1
College	2	3,2	2	3,2	4	3,2
Total	63	100	63	100	126	100

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Job						
Housewife	59	93,7	59	93,7	118	93,7
work	4	6,3	4	6,3	8	6,3
Total	63	100	63	100	126	100
Income						
< Rp. 3.413.666	60	95,2	61	96,8	124	96,0
≥ Rp. 3.413.666	3	4,8	2	3,2	2	4,0
Total	63	100	63	100	126	100

In general, the educational level of pregnant women from highest to lowest is Senior High School, namely 84.1%, Junior High School, namely 12.7% and college, namely 3.2%. The education level in each research group of counseling intervention with video and counseling without video was the same, namely 84.1%.

In general, 93.7% of pregnant women in Meukek District do not work/ housewives and work, namely 6.3%, the numbers are the

same in each research group, counseling intervention with video and counseling without video.

In general, the monthly income of pregnant women's families in Meukek District is < Rp. 3,413,666, namely 96% and ≥ Rp. 3,413,666 which is 4%. Income distribution in each research group < Rp. 3,413,666 in sequence from the highest to the counseling group, namely 96.8% and the lowest to the video counseling group, namely 95.2%.

Differences between Counseling with Video Health Promotion Media and Counseling Without Video on the Level of Knowledge
Table 2. Level of Knowledge and Attitudes of Pregnant Women About the First 1000 Days of Life Between Research Groups

Research Group	Knowledge		P- Value	Attitude		P- Value
	N	Mean Rank		N	Mean Rank	
Extension Intervention with Video	63	66,07	.425	63	73,67	.002
Extension Intervention Without Video	63	60,93		63	53,33	
Total	126			126		

Based on the table above, the highest level of knowledge is for pregnant women who received counseling intervention using video health promotion media, namely 66.07, and pregnant women who received counseling intervention without video media, namely 60.93. This shows that counseling using video media has more influence in increasing knowledge. However, statistically this is not significant because the value obtained is $P = 0.425$. Because the P value $> \alpha = 0.05$, statistically it can be concluded that the level of knowledge of pregnant women who received counseling intervention using video is the same as the level of knowledge of pregnant women who received counseling intervention without video media.

The highest attitude of pregnant women was pregnant women who received counseling intervention with video health promotion media, namely 73.67 and the lowest was pregnant women who received counseling intervention without health promotion media, namely 53.33. This shows that counseling with video health promotion media is more effective than counseling without health promotion media in improving attitudes. From the analysis test, the value of $P = 0.002$ was obtained. Because the P value $< \alpha$ value $= 0.05$, statistically it can be concluded that the attitude of pregnant women who

received counseling intervention using video health promotion media is higher than the attitude of pregnant women who received counseling intervention without health promotion media.

A person's attitude is influenced by experience, personality interests, family, social status and the success they have had in education or work. Attitudes are sometimes difficult to change and greatly influence a person's life values. attitudes that are formed from bad experiences, lack of attention during childhood makes it very difficult to change attitudes in a better direction, so to change attitudes you need to get other experiences and understanding that can prove the error of forming these attitudes (Gunarsa, 2006).

This is influenced by the respondent's perception and intensity of attention at the time of the intervention. The most common way to become knowledgeable is also called learning by remembering the encouragement received, learning will create long-lasting changes and cognitive development where after receiving educational intervention a person will be able to achieve what they could not achieve before receiving the intervention.

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This research is in line with a study conducted by (Kurniatin, 2022) showing the impact of knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women before and after receiving video-based education about the first 1000 days of life in fighting stunting. The results of this study are also the same as research conducted (Hana, 2021) which describes an increase in the level of

knowledge after nutrition education via video platforms among breastfeeding mothers. Other scientific research shows that there is an increase in knowledge after receiving counseling in the first 1000 days of life for couples of childbearing age in urban and rural environments (Al Rahmad, 2019).

Knowledge Level of Pregnant Women Before and After Being Given Intervention

Table 3. Level of Knowledge of Pregnant Women About the First 1000 Days of Life Pretest and Posttest

Variable		Pretest-posttest Knowledge				P- Value
		Negatif Ranks	Positif Ranks	Ties	Total	
Extension with Video	Intervention	1 ^a	56 ^b	6 ^c	63	.001
Extension Without Video	Intervention	0 ^a	61 ^b	2 ^c	63	.001

Based on table 3 above, it shows that after being given counseling intervention using video health promotion media, 1 respondent's knowledge decreased, 56 respondents' knowledge increased and 6 respondents remained the same. The statistical test results obtained a value of $P = 0.001 < \alpha = 0.05$, so statistically it can be concluded that there is an increase in the knowledge of pregnant women after providing intervention with counseling using video health promotion media about the first 1000 days of life in Meukek District.

In the group that was given counseling intervention without health promotion media, 0 respondents decreased their knowledge, 61 respondents increased their knowledge and 2 respondents remained the same. The statistical test results obtained a value of $P = 0.001 < \alpha \text{ value} = 0.05$, so statistically it can be concluded that there was an increase in the knowledge of pregnant women after providing intervention with counseling without videos about the first 1000 days of life in Meukek District.

The use of video health promotion media as a tool to help make the research process interesting and effective with the hope of

having many points of view that can be taken by respondents through their senses of sight and hearing, as stated by Hardianti & Asri (2017) that video media is a form of media. Audio visuals are widely applied in learning because they can increase learning effectiveness. Video media can display images (visual) and sound (audio) simultaneously when providing a message or education so that it can attract the attention of the message recipient.

Another opinion says that the benefits of video are that it can present information, understand cycles, understand confusing ideas, and have an impact on many people because as a video medium someone can hear and see directly so that a desire to learn to increase their knowledge arises (Salsabila et al., 2022). Researchers also used counseling interventions without video media. A study conducted by Asiah (2016) showed that counseling was considered effective in increasing knowledge. This research is in line with that carried out by Iyong et al., (2020) regarding increasing knowledge about balanced nutrition after receiving health education.

Attitudes of Pregnant Women Before and After Being Given Intervention

Table 4. Attitudes of pregnant women regarding the first 1000 days of life, pretest and posttest

Variable		Pretest-posttest attitude				P- Value
		Negatif Ranks	Positif Ranks	Ties	Total	
Extension with Video	Intervention	1 ^d	54 ^e	8 ^f	63	.001
Extension Without Video	Intervention	1 ^d	43 ^e	19 ^f	63	.001

Based on table 4 above, it shows that after being given counseling intervention using video health promotion media, 1 respondent's attitude decreased, 54 respondents' attitude improved and 8 respondents remained the same. The statistical

test results obtained a value of $P = 0.001 < \alpha \text{ value} = 0.05$ so that statistically it can be concluded that there was an increase in the attitude of pregnant women after providing intervention

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with counseling using video media about the first 1000 days of life in Meukek District.

In the group that was given counseling intervention without health promotion media, 1 respondent's attitude decreased, 43 respondents' attitude increased and 19 respondents remained the same. The statistical test results obtained a value of $P = 0.001 < \alpha \text{ value} = 0.05$, so statistically it can be concluded that there was an increase in the attitude of pregnant women after providing intervention with counseling without video media about the first 1000 days of life in Meukek District.

This study is in line with a study conducted by Kartikawati et al., (2020) which shows the important impact of using video media for health education on individual attitudes and intentions towards using the IUD. Research by Aisah et al., (2021) shows that there is an influence on patient knowledge and attitudes in age groups and disease groups after being given counseling interventions using animated video media. The use of video media is preferred not only because it is attractive in terms of appearance but also has attractive sound so that respondents feel that the information provided is clearer and feel happy during the process of transferring information. Apart from that, videos given over a certain period of time can change behavior, attitudes and healthy lifestyles.

Video media has the ability to disseminate information, reveal procedures, explain complex ideas, impart skills, compress or extend time, and shape attitudes, making it a valuable instructional tool in the fields of education and training (Oktaviani, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Counseling using video health promotion media and counseling without video media have a significant influence in increasing the knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women about the first 1000 days of life.

There was an increase in knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women about the first 1000 days of life after providing intervention with counseling using video health promotion media and counseling without video media.

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